

Effects of Glutamate and Acetylcholine on Foraging Behaviors of *Dugesia* sp.

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Abstract. Planarians are one of the most primitive groups of organisms to have developed a central nervous system, being a useful model for neurological research. This experiment focused on the foraging behavior of *Dugesia* sp., a freshwater planarian under the treatment of different concentrations of exogenous neurotransmitters glutamate and acetylcholine. The average velocities of planarians showed dose-related decreasing trends when acetylcholine was applied, while an overall increase was observed in all glutamate groups. Thus, the results suggested the role of the two neurotransmitters in regulating planarian motility, meanwhile providing insights towards the evolution of vertebrates.

Keywords: planaria, neurotransmitters, behavior, acetylcholine, glutamate

1. Introduction

Planarians, more commonly known as flatworms, are a member of the class Platyhelminthes, and are one of the most primitive species to have a Centralized Nervous System (CNS)^[1], which has been described as a ‘true brain’^[2]. Despite being low in the phylogenetic tree, their neurobiology is surprisingly similar to vertebrates, sharing several common neurotransmitters used by humans such as glutamic acid, acetylcholine, serotonin and dopamine. The early presence of such neurotransmitters in evolution enhances understanding in the development of human nervous systems. Platyhelminthes' small size and relatively simple structure make them ideal organisms for behavioral analysis. Their behaviors can be modeled to a set of repertoires, enabling semi-qualitative analysis; their locomotion can be quantified in several dimensions such as velocity, number of turns and displacement^[3]. Platyhelminthes' ability to absorb high molecular weight chemicals by epithelial diffusion enables exogenous application of chemicals, especially neurotransmitters, their precursors, agonists and inhibitors^[4]. Therefore, planarians serve as a prototype in neurological investigations, providing insight for neuronal machinery of human brains. This experiment used *Dugesia* sp., a representative freshwater planarian that was frequently used in behavior research^[3].

Acetylcholine is a ubiquitous neuro-muscular transmitter present in both CNS and the neuromuscular junctions in humans. Histochemical localization carried out on planarians demonstrated acetylcholinesterase activity in Platyhelminthes' submuscular nerve plexuses^[5], and cholinergic system have been suggested as one of the mediator systems for them^[6]. In terms of behavior, exogenous administration of acetylcholine elicits contradictory responses in different studies: some reported it serves as a stimulant, causing increase in muscle contraction and motility^[7-9]; whereas some argue it inhibits muscle contraction---a symptom called flaccid paralysis^[10,11], or no effect^[12]. Nevertheless, it is evident that acetylcholine participates in the neuromuscular system in flatworms.

Glutamate is the main excitatory neurotransmitter in vertebrates as well as invertebrates^[13], but less investigated than acetylcholine. L-glutamate is proposed to induce dose-related paroxysms in planarians^[14], which suggests its role in regulating motor activities; at certain concentrations this amino acid causes a mixture of large and small currents in a nerve cord. These provide convincing evidence for the presence of glutaminergic system in flatworms.

Compared to serotonin, which is known for its role in flatworm tissue regeneration, fewer researches are conducted for acetylcholine and glutamate. Hitherto most experiments aiming effect of these two neurotransmitters are either morphological—shape changes of its bodies—or neurological, which records nerve impulses^[15]. This experiment aims to analyze the effects from a locomotive perspective, focusing on the pathways chosen by flatworms when facing a food stimulus and the average velocities of them in different solutions.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Animals

The planarian *Dugesia* sp. from Dr. Zhang's lab (Shenzhen University) are cultured in dechlorinated drinkable tap water in an 18×27×33cm plastic (PET) container, kept at room temperature and away from direct light source. A clean air pump was immersed in water for ensuring oxygen level. After being fed with fresh pig liver pieces and then exchanging water on 13th August 2022, the flatworms were fasted for 11 days until the day of experiment.

2.2. Compounds

Lyophilized 100 g L-glutamic acid powder (purity ≥ 99.0%) and 5 g acetylcholine chloride powder (purity ≥ 98.0%) were bought from Hefei Bomei Biotechnology. Glutamate was stored under room temperature, acetylcholine chloride at 4 °C.

Before the experiment, 7.36 g glutamate was weighed and mixed with 1000 mL tap water to prepare 0.05M solution, then it was serially diluted to 10⁻³M, 10⁻⁴M and 10⁻⁵M solution with the aid of a 1mL pipette. These three concentrations were chosen since they were used most often by previous researches^[8,10-12,16], proving the dose not fatal, and were more effective than others.

Acetylcholine chloride (4.54g) was mixed with 250 mL tap water (sit overnight to reduce chlorine level) to prepare 0.1M solution, then serially diluted to 10⁻³ M, 10⁻⁴M and 10⁻⁵M solution. Similarly, the concentrations were picked because of their effectiveness and non-fatality^[12,14,17].

2.3. Recording

An infra-red camera from Daphnia.Net company (Shenzhen, China) was used as the recording apparatus, fixed on an iron stand, just above an acrylic box with infra-red LEDs positioned underneath (wavelength 850 nm). Infra-red light is chosen since flatworms are not sensitive to red light^[18]. To eliminate negative phototaxis of planarians, a custom-built cupboard box was used to create a dark room for the recording process. The camera was connected to a Huawei pad for video saving (see Figure 1).

Twenty-one plastic petri dishes of diameter 85mm and height 15mm were prepared. On the bottom two points, on 15mm and 70mm position of the diameter were marked using marker pen, one for placement of liver, the other for flatworm (see Figure 2)^[19]. The trial names were labelled on their lid, three for each concentration of one neurotransmitter, and three for control groups. Corresponding solutions (25 mL) were added into the dish respectively. At the time the trial was carried out, the box was lifted, and the petri dish was put on the middle of the acrylic stage, the pig liver was positioned on one mark, then within 30 secs one flatworm was transferred gently to the other mark on the petri dish with a brush. Recording

started as soon as the flatworm was positioned, and the cupboard was replaced immediately.

Figure 1. Diagram of imaging tracking device

Recordings were stopped if the flatworm were attached to liver or its pharynx had reached out, which signified feeding taking place^[3]. Otherwise, if the flatworm were scrunched up after being immobile for some time, the recording would also stop at the 20th minute, since it would be less responsive to stimulus and thus unlikely to find food later^[3].

Figure 2: Screenshot of the raw video data. The dark brown object on the middle left of the petri

dish is the flatworm, the bigger black dot is the pig liver. The ruler placed on the left is for calibration.

All 21 trials were carried out between 18:00 and 2:30, considering their nocturnal nature [12].

3. Analysis

A set of customized video tracking algorithms was run to mark points that assemble the pathway each flatworm took, and the coordinates of each point were recorded in a document, which was further run in another distance-calculating algorithm in Visual Studio Code. The results were converted from pixels to mm by calibrating it with the ruler put beside the petri dish during recording (see figure S1 in Appendix). For each video, the time before flatworm completely stopped was recorded. By dividing the displacement by time, the average speed of each flatworm could be obtained.

Independent Student t-tests were carried out separately for each concentration of neurotransmitter, with the control group as the baseline.

4. Results

Both neurotransmitters have no effect on the activity of the flatworm (Figure 3, $p > 0.05$). Though statistically insignificant, certain trends could be observed from the average velocities.

Figure 3. Average velocities of flatworms in different groups. Ach: Acetylcholine; Glu: Glutamate. The numbers 5,4,3 representing the concentrations of 10^{-5} M, 10^{-4} M and 10^{-3} M, respectively.

Change of velocity can be observed in groups treated with acetylcholine: as concentration

increases, the average velocity of flatworm decreased (see Figure 1).

Glutamate does not elicit dose-dependent effect, while flatworms' average movement sped up in all three concentrations, compared to the control group.

In terms of feeding behavior, 2 out of 3 trials (66.7%) in the control group ingested food, one in 10^{-5} M acetylcholine group (11.1%), one in 10^{-4} M glutamate group (11%).

5. Discussion

The result fails to show acetylcholine and glutamate as regulators of flatworms' behaviors in a statistically significant way. This may be owing to insufficient replicates failing to alleviate individual variances, especially in the control group (see Figure 4). As the baseline of the t-tests, the high standard deviation of the three controls raised all p values higher than expected. If more experimental data is collected, more reliable results could be obtained, and other statistical tests, Kruskal-Wallis test for example, can be utilized to check for significance.

Figure 4. The pathways taken by the three flatworms in the control group. The total distance traveled of individual flatworms, both in pixels and millimeters, are recorded in the down left corner of each diagram.

It is worth noting that flatworms tend to delay feeding in environments they are not habituated^[20], and undoubtedly there are possibilities that the unfamiliar petri dish environment will result in unwillingness to forage. However, in the control groups flatworms successfully completed feeding in 2 out of 3 trials, suggesting the effect of novel environmental stimulus contributed little to choice of feeding. Nevertheless, further experiments can be conducted with repeated preexposure to the petri dish for the planarians to acclimate. Pretreatment of chemicals towards flatworms before experiment may also alleviate the reactive response of flatworms.

Flaws in the design of the experiment are also possible sources of errors. The size of the pig liver pieces placed in the petri-dish were not unified, varying in shape and size, some also dissociated during the experiment. This caused an unpredictable difference in diffusion rate of chemoattractant, which means some flatworms were able to detect stimulus easier than others. The variation in controlled variable could disrupt the test results. In order to create a

homogenous chemical diffusion gradient, the liver can be autoclaved, liquids centrifuged, and the supernatant extracted, mixed with agarose gel solution. Pellets can be made by dipping some 30 μL solution onto a parafilm and freeze^[19].

The process of feeding is regulated by several different factors, including but not limited to ability to voluntarily contract muscles for movements and appetite. One is unable to determine which factor was affected during the experiment. The difficulty in investigating the true impact of neurotransmitters with locomotive analysis creates obstacles for reaching a conclusion.

In spite of the lack of salience of the data, observable differences provide insight for the behavioral impact of the two neurotransmitters. It can be inferred that increase in acetylcholine level mildly contributes to a reduction in speed, a possible result of muscle paralysis. This is concordant to the statements of some researchers to a certain extent^[9-11], but contradicted to observations of others^[8,16]. A plausible explanation for the discrepancy is the difference of species used. The species that increase muscle contractions are *Bdelloura candida* and *Procerodes littoralis*, both marine-living flatworms; whereas the reports revealing inhibitory effect in muscle action uses *Schistosoma mansoni*, *Fasciola hepatica* and *Hymenolepis diminuta*, all of which strongly parasitic towards humans or terrestrial animals. The implication of this is that *Dugesia* sp., a free-living freshwater planarian, assembles parasitic species more than marine ones. A potential investigation approach would be discovering the difference in neurology between free-living and parasitic, or freshwater and marine flatworms.

Glutamate shows a general stimulatory effect in flatworm activity, probably signifying an increase in muscle contraction facilitating motion. This gives support to the works of Thompson & Mettrick^[21], though they experimented on *Hymenolepis diminuta*, a parasite of rats. This suggests *Dugesia* and *Hymenolepis* have similar glutaminergic systems. The fact that glutamate is also the major excitatory neurotransmitter in mammalian central nervous system suggests the glutaminergic system was developed early in phylogeny, and retained during evolution^[22].

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Appendix:

Figure S1. The figures show the pathways drawn by the video-tracking algorithms. The first row shows the three replicates of control group, the 2 to 4 rows for acetylcholine in decreasing concentrations, and 5 to 7 rows for glutamate in decreasing concentrations.